

ACIDOID BEHAVIOUR OF CHARCOAL, AS A FUNCTION OF ITS OXYGEN COMPLEXES. PART II. INTERACTION OF CHARCOAL WITH SALT SOLUTIONS

By BALWANT RAI PURI, GURCHARAN SINGH AND LEKH RAJ SHARMA

The interaction of a few samples of charcoal with sodium, potassium and barium salts of a few organic acids has been studied and the results interpreted on the basis of distribution of a base between two weak acids. The relative strengths of the acids obtained by the data are quite close to the theoretical values, irrespective of the nature of the charcoal or that of the salt used.

A good deal of work, as summed up by Bancroft ("Applied Colloid Chemistry", 1932, 3rd ed., p. 112, McGraw-Hill Book Co., N.Y.) and Steenberg ("Adsorption and Exchange of Ions on Activated Charcoal", 1944, Almqvist and Wiksells, Uppsala), has been done on the adsorption of electrolytes by charcoal. The results, particularly in the case of salt solutions, have been often at variance and some times even contradictory, and have been variously interpreted as 'molecular adsorption' or 'exchange adsorption' or 'hydrolytic adsorption'. As shown by the authors in Part I of the series (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 357) as well as elsewhere (Puri *et al.*, *Chemistry & Industry*, 1956, B.I.F.R., 30; this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 219; 1956, **33**, 781), charcoal, on account of the presence of carbon dioxide in the surface complex, undergoes surface ionisation, when suspended in water, yielding hydrogen ions directed towards the liquid phase, and thus behaves as a weak insoluble acid or acidoid. The interaction of charcoal with alkalis, which may be represented by the equation,

proceeds to completion for any amount of the alkali added, as already shown, because one of the products of the reaction, namely water, is practically unionised and the back reaction is almost entirely absent. But its interaction with a salt solution, which may be represented by the equation,

is likely to come to a state of equilibrium for any given amount of the salt MA added, resulting in the formation of a definite amount of the free acid. The 'free' H⁺ ions of this acid may enter into an exchange competition with the free H⁺ ions of the charcoal acidoid for the M⁺ ions. The reaction, in other words, may be similar to that of the distribution of a base between two acids in which the state of equilibrium is governed by the relative strengths of the acids. If this view is correct, the liberation of free acid from a neutral solution by a "base adsorbent" charcoal—the so-called hydrolytic adsorption—may be satisfactorily explained as a simple common reaction occurring between acids

and bases. An attempt has been made in this communication to ascertain how far this view is tenable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Adsorbents.—Four different samples of charcoal, obtained by the carbonisation of cane sugar, coconut shell, pine wood and cotton stalks, were used. Sugar charcoal was almost free of ash, while the other samples were extracted with hydrofluoric acid to lower their ash content to about 0.2%. The samples were exposed to oxygen for about 12 hours as described previously. A portion of each sample was evacuated at 1200° to free it of its oxygen complexes so that the interaction with salt solutions might be studied in the absence of the oxygen complexes as well. All the samples were invariably degassed at the room temperature before examination.

Base-acid Adsorption.—The capacity of charcoal to neutralise sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and barium hydroxide was determined in the manner described before (*loc. cit.*). Briefly, 1 g. of charcoal was shaken with 80 c.c. of 0.2 *N* alkali for about 48 hours after which the excess of the alkali was determined by titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution. The alkalis were found to be adsorbed 'irreversibly' (in the sense that very little of these could be removed, by washing with water) and in almost equivalent amounts as before (*loc. cit.*) and the average values were found to be 570.4, 370.0, 350.0, 320.0 m.e./100 g. for sugar, coconut-shell, pine-wood and cotton-stalk charcoals respectively. Adsorption of formic, acetic, propionic, butyric, lactic, tartaric, citric, succinic, benzoic and salicylic acids was also determined by following a similar procedure. The amounts adsorbed were, however, very small and not at all in equivalent proportions and, unlike alkalis, could be recovered on mere washing the charcoal with hot water.

Interaction with Salt Solutions.—Decinormal solutions of formates, acetates, propionates, butyrates, lactates, tartrates, citrates and succinates of sodium, potassium and barium were prepared. Each solution (50 c.c.) was mixed with as much of charcoal as contained an equivalent amount (*i.e.*, 5 m.e.) of the acidoid. It is evident from the base-adsorption values given above that the amounts of the charcoal's containing this amount would be 0.8764, 1.3513, 1.4285 and 1.5625 g. for sugar, coconut-shell, pine-wood and cotton-stalk charcoals respectively. The suspensions were shaken for about 48 hours for the attainment of equilibrium and aliquots of the clear supernatant liquids were examined for the free acid produced and the metallic cations left in solution; the former by titrating against a standard alkali solution and the latter, in the case of barium salts, by precipitating as barium sulphate, and in the case of sodium and potassium salts, by treating with excess of hydrochloric acid and estimating the amount of sodium chloride and potassium chloride left as residue on evaporating to dryness.

The charcoal, after washing, was examined in each case for the amounts of the cations fixed on it by treatment with excess hydrochloric acid and estimating the amounts of sodium, potassium and barium chloride (as the case may be) brought into solution, as described in Part I of the series (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I
Interaction of charcoals with aqueous salt solutions.

Salt solution.	Sugar charcoal.		Coconut-shell charcoal.		Pine-wood charcoal.		Cotton-stalk charcoal.			
	Acid liberated (m.e.).	Cations removed from soln. on C (m.e.).	Acid liberated (m.e.).	Cations removed from soln. on C (m.e.).	Acid liberated (m.e.).	Cations removed from soln. on C (m.e.).	Acid liberated (m.e.).	Cations removed from soln. on C (m.e.).		
Formate	0.2100	0.2085	0.2140	0.2010	0.2223	0.2087	0.2128	0.2058	0.1989	0.2062
Acetate	0.6333	0.6023	0.6087	0.5987	0.5872	0.6344	0.5399	0.5728	0.5444	0.5566
Propionate	0.6346	0.6776	0.6210	0.6129	0.6038	0.6141	0.6040	0.5890	0.6022	0.6201
Butyrate	0.7025	0.7443	0.6723	0.6645	0.5923	0.5996	0.5899	0.6336	0.6431	0.6508
Lactate	0.2312	0.2117	0.2018	0.2210	0.2191	0.2274	0.2299	0.1987	0.2042	0.1828
Benzoate	0.2987	0.3034	0.3334	0.3196	0.2976	0.3033	0.2843	0.2044	0.2856	0.2877
Salicylate	0.1173	0.1301	0.1276	0.1241	0.1044	0.1147	0.0987	0.0995	0.1131	0.1212
			Barium salt.							
Formate	0.2000	0.2110	0.2072	0.1988	0.2112	0.2075	0.2057	0.2018	0.2072	0.1890
Acetate	0.6524	0.6439	0.6474	0.6500	0.5729	0.5932	0.4844	0.5720	0.5874	0.5566
Propionate	0.5978	0.6122	0.5992	0.6200	0.5876	0.5699	0.5771	0.5973	0.6074	0.6560
Butyrate	0.6346	0.6414	0.6013	0.5876	0.5922	0.6164	0.6522	0.5870	0.5999	0.5733
Lactate	0.2170	0.2089	0.2334	0.2314	0.2392	0.2277	0.2442	0.2190	0.2085	0.2281
Benzoate	0.2785	0.2870	0.2791	0.2804	0.2762	0.2696	0.2885	0.2773	0.2804	0.2786
Salicylate	0.0926	0.1010	0.0922	0.1117	0.1214	0.1320	0.1219	0.1170	0.0947	0.1076
Succinate	0.4104	0.4049	0.4103	0.3987	0.3840	0.3943	0.3727	0.3818	0.3702	0.3668
Carbonate	0.000	2.3410	...	2.5780	...	2.3970	2.4320	...	2.3460	2.2980
			Sodium salt.							
Formate	0.2088	0.2104	0.2190	0.2227	0.2018	0.1988	0.2113	0.2020	0.2216	0.1967
Acetate	0.6724	0.6587	0.6567	0.6474	0.6111	0.6040	0.5871	0.6187	0.5970	0.4955
Propionate	0.6740	0.6411	0.6341	0.6151	0.6310	0.6174	0.6597	0.6725	0.6555	0.6925
Butyrate	0.6872	0.6674	0.6429	0.6244	0.6189	0.6077	0.6384	0.5913	0.5989	0.5768
Lactate	0.4410	0.2257	0.2123	0.2088	0.2117	0.2304	0.2200	0.2265	0.2112	0.2218
Benzoate	0.3317	0.3220	0.3116	0.3039	0.3117	0.3310	0.3228	0.3114	0.3277	0.3257
Salicylate	0.4200	0.4141	0.4120	0.4154	0.4122	0.4087	0.4041	0.4089	0.0999	0.1112
Succinate	0.4510	0.4446	0.4170	0.4152	0.4491	0.4128	0.4133	0.3970	0.4014	0.3668
Carbonate	...	2.2980	...	2.3710	...	2.3140	2.2692	...	2.2740	2.2260

TABLE II
Relative strengths of acids with respect to charcoal acidoid.

Salt soln.	The ratio : $\frac{\text{Amount of ions in soln.}}{\text{Amount of ions fixed on } ^\circ\text{C}}$				in case of $\sqrt{\frac{K_a}{K_{\text{carbonic acid}}}}$
	Sugar.	Coconut-shell.	charcoal from Pine-wood.		
A. Formate.					
Na	23.78	22.99	23.30	25.45	
K	22.27	21.49	22.66	24.41	22.43
Ba	22.84	23.75	22.48	23.25	
B. Acetate					
Na	6.46	6.64	9.32	7.84	
K	6.24	6.62	7.51	9.29	7.05
Ba	6.93	8.12	8.26	7.83	
C. Propionate.					
Na	6.87	7.54	7.66	6.62	
K	5.30	6.96	6.58	6.24	6.32
Ba	6.17	7.39	7.27	7.06	
D. Butyrate.					
Na	6.16	7.99	6.67	7.72	
K	6.03	6.63	6.83	7.66	6.50
Ba	5.90	6.63	7.47	6.62	
E. Lactate.					
Na	24.93	20.77	19.50	20.93	
K	21.67	21.08	21.73	21.54	21.05
Ba	19.68	22.81	20.74	26.33	
F. Benzoate.					
Na	15.90	16.61	16.30	17.90	
K	12.97	16.58	14.49	14.35	13.80
Ba	12.73	14.33	16.51	16.37	
G. Salicylate.					
Na	36.93	49.60	40.01	45.47	
K	48.30	51.08	47.03	43.66	55.03
Ba	37.97	39.28	49.65	40.25	
H. Succinate.					
Na	12.16	10.52	12.41	12.86	
K	10.63	10.23	10.59	12.85	13.52
I. Carbonate.					
Na	1.09	0.95	1.06	1.18	
K	1.13	1.06	1.20	1.24	1.00

DISCUSSION

If the interaction of charcoal with salt solutions takes place as represented by the equation given above, the amount of the acid set free should be equivalent to the metal cations which disappear from solution and which are fixed.

on charcoal surface. Further, as the quantities of the various charcoals mixed with the salt solutions were such as contained an equivalent amount of the acidoid, these values for a given salt should also be the same in every case. That this is actually so is evident from the data presented in Table I. Now as the charcoal acidoid and salt solutions were mixed initially in equivalent proportions, the equilibrium concentrations permitted the determination of the relative strengths of the acids concerned with respect to that of the charcoal acidoid. The ratios of the amounts of the metal cations found in solution to those fixed on charcoal, at the equilibrium stage, are compared with the square roots of the ratios of the dissociation constants of the acids concerned to that of carbonic acid (relative strengths) in Table II. It is interesting to note that in every case the ratio of the amount of the base held by the acid to that fixed on the charcoal is nearly the same and quite close to the relative strength of the acid radical of the salt with respect to carbonic acid. It appears quite significant that the values obtained for a particular acid are almost identical, irrespective of the nature of its salt or that of the charcoal used in these experiments. This agreement also shows that in each variety of charcoal we are having the same acidoid and supports the view previously expressed on the basis of titration curves (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1957) as well as measurements of heats of neutralisation of alkalies by charcoals (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1955) that acidoid character of charcoal is due to the presence of carbonic acid in its surface oxygen complexes. It is also interesting to note that in the case of equilibrium with alkali carbonates, when the same acid, namely carbonic acid, is supposed to be competing for the base on either side of the equation, the amount of the base held on the charcoal and that found in solution are almost the same.

It may be mentioned that the charcoal samples freed of CO₂-complex on degassing at 1200° could neither take up bases nor produce any change in the concentration of the salt solutions.

The results presented above support the view that interaction of charcoal with salt solutions is similar to the reaction involving the distribution of a base between two weak acids. The fact that one of the acids is an acidoid does not make any difference to the treatment of the reaction.